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Student Perceptions of Complexity in Engineering Education

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ABSTRACT

The complex and socially connected nature of modern engineering practice is well documented, motivating new approaches to engineering education across the globe. The challenge now is to bring about change at scale to traditional curricula [1].

The University of Sydney has implemented a core program designed to improve students' learning and preparation for professional practice. The program seeks to help students develop an appreciation of complexity in engineering practice and illustrate its interdisciplinary, connected nature. The program serves a cohort of ~800 commencing students annually and is delivered within the bounds of a traditional program structured in units of study. Standardised student satisfaction survey results have been below or well below faculty average, indicating that on this measure, a majority of students are not satisfied with their learning experience. To better understand why, student comments on these surveys were analysed through the lens of the Cynefin framework, a sense-making tool that provides a useful characterisation of complexity experienced in professional engineering [2, 3].

Analysis suggest students may be aligned along a continuum between two positions in regard to the perceived degree of complexity in the learning experience: *Comfortable with complexity* – Those who recognise and adopt strategies needed to succeed in complex projects; and, *Resistance to complexity* – Those who see the learning design as unsupportive and unnecessarily ambiguous.

The results highlight issues around student perspectives of what 'learning' is, as well as structural issues existing within standardised student satisfaction surveys, each of which pose potential barriers to curriculum reform.

1 INTRODUCTION

The Faculty of Engineering at the University of Sydney began implementing an Integrated Engineering (IE) program consisting of four core units of study, one for each academic year, across all engineering majors in 2016.

The units are delivered alongside the standard array of engineering disciplinary units. Students work in cross-disciplinary teams on projects intentionally designed to help them engage with peers undertaking disciplinary studies other than their own. While complex systems are a fundamental aspect of many domains, they are especially characteristic of engineering. The IE program is designed to improve students' appreciation of the complexity they can expect to find in engineering practice and illustrate its interdisciplinary, interconnected nature. Once fully implemented the program will engage with up to 3600+ students per year.

This paper presents the findings of a qualitative analysis of 778 student satisfaction survey responses received from students in each of the four IE units. The goal of the research is to gain insight into factors that influence student adoption of / comfort with complexity and/or their resistance to complexity designed into the program. It is anticipated that this in turn will help to inform the design and implementation of educational practices for supporting the transition of novice engineering students into early career professionals who are aware of the complex nature of their probable future workplaces.

1.1 Difficult vs Complex - creating workplace-oriented learning spaces

In engineering practice, activities are rarely characterised by an ideal answer but rather are complex, requiring trade-offs and/or the combining of non-optimum solutions. Hence, to authentically develop engineering skills, students need to learn to manage complexity. Many students resist working with complexity, describing it as too difficult, too much work, less valuable and not real engineering [4]. Dealing with complexity requires students to use judgement, subjectivity, and reasoning to make decisions instead of relying primarily on the scientific evidence and facts that are often more highly valued by engineering academics and students [4]. Many engineering students resist this change, expecting their learning to be the simple transition from the 'knowable' to the 'known' [2], finding it difficult to make the transition from dichotomous reasoning to thinking contextually and dialectically. This transition challenges students' feelings of competency. Self-determination theory [5] lists competence as one of three basic cognitive needs required for motivation. Reduced feelings of competence inhibits students' learning motivation and their interest in addressing and benefiting from complex learning activities.

Since the IE Program focuses on educational and assessment practices intended to enable students to improve their capacity for managing complexity, it is important to be clear about the distinction between two related terms, 'difficult' and 'complex', which are frequently, and incorrectly, used interchangeably. Things that are '*difficult*' are hard to do, make, or carry out. In a physical context they may be arduous and hard to deal with, manage, or overcome. In an intellectual sense they may be hard to understand and puzzling. However, in all contexts there are known and knowable solutions that are repeatable.

Conversely, things that are '*complex*' have no readily achievable solution and remain problematic, in that any outcome will not necessarily fit any future similar context.

Thus, complexity can be explored and instances resolved, but solutions have remaining uncertainty that may only be resolved, if at all, in retrospect after implementation [2] [4]. The term ‘wicked problem’ is often applied to issues identified as complex.

Difficult can be characterized as a perspective. *Difficult things* become easier through acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills, and experience. *Complex*, by contrast is an attribute; more knowledge and enhanced skills do not of themselves change anything. *Complex* is always *complex*, regardless of knowledge, skill and experience. Kurtz and Snowden [2] provide a very useful characterisation of *complex* in relation to other attributes of a problem or scenario (see Fig. 1). IE projects are situated in the Complex domain, characterised as ‘Un-Order,’ while traditional teaching modes tend to be centred in the Visible and Hidden domains characterised as ‘Order’. In the latter domains problems, projects etc. tend to be resolved through well established paths applying the ‘right’ knowledge and skill and with appropriate support.

Fig. 1. The Cynefin Domains of Knowledge [2]

Teaching and learning processes used in Integrated Engineering units focus on building students' capacity to manage issues arising in the Complex domain more effectively, while recognising that each encounter has unique non-repeatable characteristics. Projects to be completed, and the educational designs that facilitate them, are not intended to lead students to pre-defined ‘answers’ or ‘resolutions’ since these do not arise in the Complex domain. To illustrate, consider the design of a bridge, an easily recognisable ‘complex’ problem. There are multiple options, each having benefits and drawbacks. However, once it is decided to complete the bridge, the outcome, while perhaps not the best of all possible solutions, is the one agreed to be the most appropriate fit given all contemporary constraints and opportunities. Moreover, the same solution will not be directly applicable the next time a similar task arises.

Thus, the educational strategy underlying the IE suite is intended to support students in developing judgement, acquiring the capacity to work effectively in the face of multiple possibilities, competing demands and assumptions, through creating original, well founded and argued solutions to complex real problems. This is achieved through three essential components of the curriculum [adapted from 6]:

1. learners taking action to create contextually relevant knowledge;
2. aligning methods chosen for engagement with the course content and its underlying principles (ie. simulation of industry practices); and,
3. utilising assessment tasks to promote ongoing learning, potentially extending learning outcomes far beyond input from the educator, peers or materials

IE, as with a range of similar experience-based learning strategies, emphasises the 'primacy of praxis', through a focus on creating environments that allow learning to follow the flow of novelty and emergent practice, rather than organizing for learning around a fixed set of lectures, highly defined exercises, and infrastructures [7 p. 22].

Instead of delivering pre-packaged 'pieces' of knowledge to be memorized, IE creates a planned sequence of learning containers enabling the emergence and growth of knowledge about, and understanding of, engineering as a contextually responsive profession. In doing so, IE can begin to unsettle student assumptions about such things as 'how to be a student', how knowledge is created, and who has authority to define and create new ideas. In effect it places the learning process and the learner's engagement with it, at the centre of the action. Thus, it is quite distinct from conventional lectures and lab work where the academic, as an external authority figure and acknowledged expert, directs the learning focus and carries the burden of all decision making.

Concurrent work in the integrated engineering program has focused on developing a language and framework for managing complexity to facilitate instructors to scaffold, articulate and model learning methods and expectations, students to be able to discuss, evaluate their competence and understand their learning, and for instructors and students to co-construct the learning outcomes and expected academic standards [4].

2 METHODOLOGY

This investigation into students' responses to this intentional focus on complexity is being undertaken as part of a larger evaluation of the IE program. This paper reports on analysis of the standardised Unit of Study Survey (USS) results - an end of semester, anonymous survey of student satisfaction conducted for all units of study. The survey is conducted online and participation is voluntary. The sample analysed here includes 778 student responses across first, second, third, and fourth year units in the program, with an average response rate of 38%.

The survey included 10 Likert scale questions typical of student satisfaction surveys. These questions solicited opinions on perceptions of learning, teaching quality, and general satisfaction. The survey also included the following open-ended response questions:

1. What have been the best aspects of this unit of study?
2. What aspects of this unit of study most need improvement?
3. Are there any other aspects of this unit of study that you would like to comment on?

Analysis of these open responses was the focus of this study. The sample covered two instances of the 1st and 2nd year units, and one each of the 3rd and 4th year units.

Table 1. Summary of survey data sample

Cohort/unit year	n	Enrolled	Response
1 st year	214	580	37%
1 st year	79	237	33%
2 nd year	26	54	48%
2 nd year	309	696	44%
3 rd year	102	321	32%
4 th year	48	168	29%

Analysis was conducted using an inductive coding approach in QSR Nvivo by an independent research assistant not involved with the teaching or design of the IE program. To preserve the conditions of anonymity and data usage originally provided to survey participants, original quotes have not been published here. Results presented are thematic analyses findings only.

3 RESULTS

Initial inductive coding of the open-ended question responses revealed a distinct dichotomy in participant sentiment towards key elements of their unit of study. These key elements were coded as:

- **Resources** (positive or negative sentiment): Course related resources that either students, lecturers or tutors utilised. Examples included handouts, lecture slides, online content, videos, assessment rubrics.
- **Activities** (positive or negative sentiment): Student class-based activities.
- **Assessment / Evaluation** (positive or negative sentiment): Both formative and summative assessment/evaluation mechanisms.
- **Lecture / Tutorial support** (positive or negative sentiment): Sentiment references to either individual Tutors or Lecturers.

Another category emerged around participant **skills or insights** (positive or negative sentiment). This category captured both direct and incidental skills students felt they had or had not gained in the program. Direct skills related closely to course learning outcomes to individual skills, such as teamwork, communication and critical thinking skills. Incidental skills also emerged as a result of the direct skills, such as improving English language skills and making new friends.

This category also captured deeper personal insights about the program. This included where students felt they had personally benefited from, or been disadvantaged by, the program. Positive insight examples included expanded insights into what Engineers do, and examples where students had gained a better understanding of engineering through exposure to real-world engineering projects. Negative insight examples included perceived excessive workload related to unit credit points, or failing to understand the purpose of the IE program.

A large majority of participant responses were expressed as either strongly positive or strongly negative in sentiment. Only a very small number of participants expressed

neutral sentiment across the open-ended response questions. It was apparent that the responses were quite polarised, with strongly positive or negative sentiments expressed around the same issue. This was also reflected in the quantitative survey questions where sentiment was typically split between positive and negative, resulting in an overall result for most survey items in each unit as neither strongly positive or negative (agreement or disagreement with the questionnaire item).

Drawing meaningful conclusions from the initial analysis was challenging. For every 'like' expressed in student comments, there appeared to be an equal and opposite 'dislike'. It was at this point that the decision was made to undertake a more structured analysis of the data to explore the extent to which perceptions of the focus on developing students' comfort with complexity were evident in responses. The categories were subsequently integrated and examined via the 'Complex' component of Cynefin theoretical framework lens with a focus on:

- What are the ways in which students indicate adoption of, or comfort with, complexity in the learning experience?
- What are the ways in which students indicate resistance to complexity in the learning experience?

Within the full sample, a total of 121 participant comments were coded as indications of comfort with or resistance to complexity in the educational design (63 – Comfort with complexity, 58 – Resistance to complexity). Responses coded as evidence of response to complexity were typically longer comments that provided insight into both the students' position, and the reasoning for it. The two high level categories were then further analysed to explore the components of the student experience that made up their prevailing comfort with or resistance to complexity. The results are presented in *Table 2*.

Table 2. Summary of themes relating to complexity in the learning experience

Comfort with complexity (no. of references)	Summary of participant comments
Relevance, authenticity and professional formation (33)	Remarks on the relevance to professional practice and 'the real world'. Skills development as important for future/other contexts, particularly professional and communication skills.
Collaboration (22)	Forming new professional connections and building networks through the learning experience. Integrating different skills of individuals.
Learning support (20)	Curriculum design or teaching staff were supportive through the learning process. Comments typically expressed in relation to support provided for working through tasks, not giving answers.
Resistance to complexity	

Lack of clarity (18)	Complaints about not being clear on tasks, seeking examples to follow. These comments typically implied that the path and the desired outcome should be made clear through the learning design.
Lack of support/Deferral of responsibility (17)	More forthright comments suggesting that students should be shown what to do throughout the process. Differentiated from 'lack of clarity' in the extent to which student assigned responsibility to teachers or curriculum. Comments on teaching staff not providing help, not 'teaching'.
Too hard, lack of value (8)	Complaints about unreasonable expectations, unreasonable level of difficulty. These comments generally implied that the skills focus of the units were not valued.
Irrelevance (19)	Comments mentioning lack of relevance tended to focus on relevance to the program of study, rather than relevance to professional practice. A minority of students also commented on the relevance to their own very specific circumstances.

4 DISCUSSION

Overall, statements made in the negative tended to have less clarity of meaning and were more varied in focus. It must be noted that those who resist complexity are not regarded as 'poor' students. Rather, the results suggest that views on what a valuable learning experience is, is influenced by their conception of what 'learning' is, or their views on the realities of engineering practice. This could be seen most clearly in the comparison between comments discussing the relevance or irrelevance of the learning. Relevance of the learning experience tended to be discussed in a positive sense in relation to professional practice, whereas it was typically discussed in the negative in relation to the wider (and more traditional) curriculum.

This is a particularly important finding for the IE program as it is delivered within a traditional engineering curriculum. As long as the learning experience in the program differs significantly from students' contemporary experience in other units, it is at risk of being viewed as an outlier, and atypical, despite its alignment with industry practices.

Students' views on what 'learning' is were also apparent in comments relating to the curriculum design and learning support offered by teaching staff. Those who were positive seemed to discuss guidance provided by tutors, or the sequenced arrangement of learning activities and assessments. Those who were negative indicated expectations of being shown what to do and being provided with exemplars to model their own work on, and attributing the difficulty they experienced to the perceived 'vagueness' of tasks.

These findings may also provide insight into the polarized nature of quantitative survey results. Some students may be reflecting on their experience in the unit at face value with respect to their preparation for an engineering career, whereas others may be comparing it to their experience of learning in other units of study and prior education.

4.1 Limitations

The use of data from standardised Unit of Study Survey (USS) results is both a strength and a weakness of this study. The voluntary nature of the survey and the anonymity of responses may have elicited a disproportionately dissatisfied (negative) sample of the student cohort.

However, the unsolicited (as in, not asking directly about complexity) remarks giving insight into complexity helped us to understand the different ways in which students resist it in the learning design. Other research undertaken in the larger IE program evaluation has involved face-to-face focus groups with students, staff and graduates, and analysis of end of semester reflective assessment submissions. These have both provided deeper insights into how student engage with the learning and navigate complexity in a predominantly positive sense. This is possibly due to the influence of the interviewer/facilitator being seen to be an employee of the institution, or the positive bias in students' responses to an assessable reflective task. The analysis of anonymous comments presented a negative perspective largely absent in these other, more targeted, data collection and analysis approaches.

5 IMPLICATIONS AND CONCLUSION

These findings have significant implications for the IE program and potentially other similar programs emerging globally. Where evaluation of teaching is largely limited to quantitative results of student satisfaction surveys, there is a high risk of support for such a curriculum innovation being undermined by 'poor' quantitative survey results that don't adequately reflect student perceptions evident in the qualitative data. The deeper analysis of qualitative results shown here suggests that the numbers don't tell the full story. The learning outcomes and curriculum design employed are in fact recognised and appreciated by a significant proportion of the cohort, while being opposed and resisted strongly by others. We must remember that these surveys evaluate student satisfaction, not necessarily their learning or their professional development. As Brookfield reports, "learning that challenges and stretches students, asks them to think critically or use their judgement to deal with uncertainty and complexity, often induces resistance" [8]. This resistance as shown in this study can result in poor student satisfaction and hence low survey scores. This highlights another issue - that we need to also develop students' ongoing learning identity trajectory. If we want students to embrace and learn from the challenges of managing complexity we need to do more to change some students' learning culture and perceptions of legitimate learning to promote engagement, participation and realise the benefits.

Furthermore, to address the potential risk of students viewing the IE program as an outlier in terms of the learning experience, the program needs to have closer connection to pedagogies used in parallel units of study. At a minimum this could be verbal endorsement of the program and linking its learning outcomes to their technical subject studies. We suggest a longer term approach would require significant changes to academic culture to integrate management of complexity into learning and assessment activities across the curriculum.

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